

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE PROGRESSIVE FAILURE OF SMC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The present work deals with the modelling of progressive failure behaviour of composites using finite element software packages. The simulations have been performed for the material models available within PAM-CRASH and LS-DYNA packages. Numerical simulations of tensile and tree-point bending tests of flat plate have been performed. Specifically, a comparison is made between the results obtained from numerical simulation using a material models already implemented into the each software.

KEYWORDS: composites, numerical analysis, SMC (sheet moulding compound) composite, progressive damage modelling

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are generally considered to be at the forefront of future development in a wide variety of disciplines, most notably the aerospace and automotive fields. However the implementation of these materials in the general automotive industry has remained limited, due in major part to a lack of knowledge regarding the crash response of these materials bringing about uncertainty regarding their safety and predictability. Thus the subject of composite material modelling has been a source of extensive research and at present many models have successfully been devised [1-3] which are found to adequately simulate the response of these materials. Some of these models are also found to be ready-implemented in commercially available analysis tools. However, an examination of the most commonly used software packages in the field of automotive crashworthiness shows that although composite material models have indeed been implemented, these models are almost entirely limited to the family of continuously reinforced composite materials, with the modelling of discontinuous (short-fibre) composites almost lacking. At present those models that are integrated into finite element analysis software generally approach the modelling of short fibre composites as isotropic materials, incorporating some form of damage law to take into account the progressive failure nature of the material. In this study, SMC based composites, are specifically focused on, and an investigation is made into the modelling of SMC composite materials through the use of two commercially available finite element analysis packages, PAM-CRASH and LS-DYNA. The results obtained from each package are compared, and an analysis is made of the numerical models present within the software, which are suitable for SMC composite modelling. The key distinction between the models that are available for SMC analysis is the inclusion and non-inclusion of a so-called ‘damage factor’, d_i ,

$$d_i = 1 - \frac{E_i}{E_{i-1}} \quad (1)$$

which takes into account the progressively fracturing nature of composite materials [4].

SMC COMPOSITE MATERIAL MODELS

The primary concern of this work is to simulate dynamic progressive damage and to investigate the modelling of SMC composite material using PAM-CRASH and LS-DYNA. The basis of this modelling lies in the manner in which the material is damaged.

The model, selected as representative of those currently available for SMC composite materials in the PAM-CRASH software, is an elastic-plastic material model incorporating isotropic progressive damage behaviour. The material is isotropic and is degraded using a damage mechanics law based on experimentally obtained results (plasticity is ignored for the purposes of SMC composite analysis).

The undamaged material constitution is defined in terms of the material elastic modulus, mass density and ‘yield stress’ (interpreted for SMC composite analysis).

Damage parameter is introduced in the material stress tensor as follows:

$$\sigma = (1 - d(\varepsilon))\sigma_0 \quad (2)$$

where σ is the full stress tensor for the damaged material,
 $d(\varepsilon)$ is the isotropic scalar damage function, a function of the strain, ε ,
and
 σ_0 is the full stress tensor as calculated according to the elastic-plastic material law (with or without strain rate effects) for the undamaged material.

The damage curve is assumed piecewise linear between three key strain points, $\varepsilon_i, \varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_u$, which are obtained from an experimental stress-strain curve for the material, and is defined in terms of the material elastic unloading moduli at each of the points as follows:

The initial damage factor,

$$d_1 = 1 - \frac{E_1}{E_0} \quad (3)$$

at ε_1 and, the ultimate damage factor,

$$d_u = 1 - \frac{E_u}{E_1} \quad (4)$$

at ε_u .

Between these defined points, d grows linearly from 0 to d_1 in the interval $\varepsilon_i \leq \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_1$, and from d_1 to d_u in the interval $\varepsilon_1 \leq \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_u$. E_0 , E_1 , and E_u are the initial (undamaged), intermediate and ultimate values of the material unloading moduli, corresponding to the slopes. Beyond the ultimate damage strain the damage function remains constant.

For simulation in LS-DYNA, due to the materials quasi-isotropic and non-linear behaviour under progressive crash, it was decided to employ an elastic-plastic material model incorporating kinematic hardening. The material constitution is defined in terms of the material elastic modulus, mass density and ‘yield stress’ (interpreted for SMC composite analysis). These characteristics could be obtained from the experimental stress-strain curves plotted for tensile and compressive loading.

SIMULATED TESTING

A series of both tensile and bending tests were simulated, at loading velocities of both 33mm/s and 330mm/s in order to additionally investigate strain rate effects. Applied tests conditions are schematically shown on Fig. 1. For the tensile case, a plate of dimensions 150 x 100 x 5 mm was loaded by the application of a prescribed velocity, v at one end of the plate, while the other end was

fixed in position. For the bending case, a prescribed constant velocity was applied to the centre of a plate of geometry identical to the tensile case, supported a third of the length from each end.

Fig. 1 Schematic tensile end bending set-up, v is the prescribed velocity.

The plates are made from the Glass-Epoxy SMC composite. Mechanical properties of the material are as follows: modulus of elasticity $E = 23.28$ GPa, Poisson’s ratio $\nu = 0.3$, density $\rho = 1.8$ g/sm³, “yield stress” $\tilde{\sigma} = 465.6$ MPa, key strain points: $\epsilon_i = 0.02$, $\epsilon_1 = 0.06$, $\epsilon_u = 0.09$, damage factors $d_l = 0.2$, $d_u = 0.9$.

SIMULATION RESULTS

Simulation results (see Figs. 2-3) for the tensile testing, from each of the two software packages, were analysed and compared on the basis of the stress and strain, at the material elastic limit and at the maximum load carrying point. Simulation results for each loading velocity showed little deviation, with a discrepancy of 7% at the maximum stress point. Comparison of the results of simulations with different velocities is shown in Tables 1-2.

Fig. 2 Tensile test simulation using LS-DYNA software (deformed plate and stress distribution).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3 Tensile test simulation using PAM-CRASH software:
(a) deformed plate and (b) force-displacement curve.

Table 1. Tensile test simulated results for SMC material (330 mm/s prescribed velocity).

Simulation results	Elastic limit (MPa)	Displacement at elastic limit (mm)	Maximum Stress (MPa)	Displacement at maximum stress (mm)
PAM-CRASH	442	2.85	456	3.50
LS-DYNA	424	3.34	424	3.34
% Deviation	4	17	7	5

Table 2. Tensile test simulated results for SMC material (33 mm/s prescribed velocity).

Simulation results	Elastic limit (MPa)	Displacement at elastic limit (mm)	Maximum Stress (MPa)	Displacement at maximum stress (mm)
PAM-CRASH	457	3.20	460	4.00
LS-DYNA	391	2.63	430	4.12
% Deviation	14	18	7	3

Simulations of three-point bending test have been performed using LS-DYNA and PAM-CRASH packages (Figs. 4-5).

Fig. 4 Bending test simulation using LS-DYNA software (deformed plate and bending moment distribution).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5 Bending test simulation using PAM-CRASH software
 (a) deformed plate and (b) force-displacement curve.

Force displacement diagrams obtained from the bending test simulations with different velocities are shown in Figs. 6-7. The bending test simulations showed a larger discrepancy, and it is in the comparison of the obtained force-displacement plots for the two models for this loading condition, that the effect of the incorporation of a progressive damage law is clearly seen.

SMC Composite Bending Test Simulation (330mm/s)

Fig. 6 Bending test simulation results (330mm/s).

SMC Composite Bending Test Simulation (33mm/s)

Fig. 7 Bending test simulation results (33mm/s).

The difference between the modelling of the material is evident from the comparative plots (see Figs. 6-7). Whereas in PAM-CRASH damage law governs the material degradation, solely plasticity effects govern the LS-DYNA model. This explains the gradual drop-off in the LS-DYNA material, as compared to the quick degradation in the PAM-CRASH case, corresponding to the points of intermediate material failure. A third plot is included above showing the curve corresponding to a PAM-CRASH simulation without implementation of the damage law. This shows the conformance of the results of the basic modelling in the two packages, and the effect of the incorporation of the damage law.

CONCLUSIONS

Numerical experimentation suggests that composite materials behave as depicted by the PAM-CRASH simulation, with definite progressive failure of the constituents evident, resulting in a truncated force-displacement curve. This truncation is controlled in the simulation by the input of experimentally obtained damage coefficients, which define the shape of the material stress-strain curve by reducing the material modulus. For practical implementation of these results, physical experimentation should be performed to characterise the SMC material fully, and for the results verification.

REFERENCES

1. Johnson, A.F. and Holzapfel, (2002), M., Computational Methods for Predicting Impact Damage in Engineering Composite Structures, WCCM V, Vienna, Austria.
2. Tita, V. and de Carvalho, J., (2001), Study on the Impact Behaviour of Composites using the Finite Element Method, Proc. of ICCM-13, Beijing.
3. Johnson, A.F. and Pickett, A.K., (1999), Impact and Crash Modeling of Composite Structures: A Challenge for Damage Mechanics, EURO-PAM '99.
4. PAM-CRASH Solver Notes, (2000), ESI Group.